

Electronic Theses and Dissertations Bibliography

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Introduction

The *Electronic Theses and Dissertations Bibliography* includes selected English-language articles and books that are useful in understanding electronic theses and dissertations.

This bibliography does not cover conference papers, digital media works (such as MP3 files), editorials, e-mail messages, interviews, letters to the editor, presentation slides or transcripts, unpublished e-prints, or weblog postings.

Most sources have been published from 2000 through 2020; however, a limited number of earlier key sources are also included. The bibliography has links to included works. Such links, even to publisher versions, are subject to change. Where possible, this bibliography uses Digital Object Identifier System (DOI) URLs.

Abstracts are included in this bibliography if a work is under a Creative Commons Attribution License (BY and national/international variations), a Creative Commons public domain dedication (CC0), or a Creative Commons Public Domain Mark and this is clearly indicated in the work (see the "Note on the Inclusion of Abstracts" below for more details).

For further information about electronic theses and dissertations, visit the websites of the [Networked Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations](#) and the [United States Electronic Thesis and Dissertation Association](#).

Dedication

In memory of [Paul Evan Peters](#) (1947-1996), founding Executive Director of the Coalition for Networked Information, whose visionary leadership at the dawn of the Internet era fostered the development of scholarly electronic publishing.

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INTRODUCTION This study compares the two most popular electronic theses and dissertation (ETD) management systems used in the American higher education community today: the commercial ProQuest dissertation publishing system and the university repository. **METHODS** Characteristics of these systems are identified and categorized to determine the features, functions, and policies common to both, and those that uniquely characterize one or the other system. Performing such a head-to-head comparison provides valuable information and insights to decision makers responsible for managing or overhauling their university's ETD program. **RESULTS** Comparison of characteristics shows the ProQuest system and the University Repository both provide functional solutions for submitting, storing, disseminating, and archiving ETD's using digital technology. Yet each system also has unique characteristics that distinguish it from the other. **DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION** The authors conclude that there is no single 'best' system for ETD management overall. Rather, it is up to decision makers at each institution to choose an approach that best fits their university's values, goals, and needs. Additionally, the authors point out the need for a single portal for ETDs that allows for search and discovery of these unique works of scholarship wherever the full text resides. Future investigation into possible solutions for such an ETD portal would be a boon not only to universities and ETD authors, but to the diverse researchers, students, professionals, and interested citizenry who could benefit from easier access to this growing corpus of knowledge.

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The preparation and publication of dissertations can be viewed as a subsystem of scholarly communication, and the treatment of data that support doctoral research can be mapped in a very controlled manner to the data curation lifecycle. Dissertation datasets represent "low-hanging fruit" for universities who are developing institutional data collections. The current workflow for processing electronic theses and dissertations (ETD) at a typical American university is presented, and a new practice is proposed that includes datasets in the process of formulating, awarding, and disseminating dissertations in a way that enables them to be linked and curated together. The value proposition and new roles for the university and its student-authors, faculty, graduate programs and librarians are explored.

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INTRODUCTION An attractive repository with clear, well-structured and accessible content can be a powerful recruitment and publicity tool for administrators, fundraisers, and others trying to bolster support for repositories. Digitizing ETDs is a lengthy and often arduous process. Once that process is completed, it is often a victory that suffices. As a result, collections frequently receive no further treatment. We demonstrate the benefits of visualizing repository content. **DESCRIPTION OF THE PROJECT** The goal of the project was to create an interactive visualization to make our newly digitized theses and dissertations more discoverable. By leveraging the institutional organization of College, Department and Year of Graduation, we visualized data to help users understand ETD content as a whole and find specific items more easily. **BUILDING THE VISUALIZATION** The process begins with data cleanup involving extracting and normalizing repository metadata, then the data is processed and the Data-Driven Documents (D3) JavaScript library is used to generate the actual visualization. **Benefits of Visualizations to Users:** The visualization allows for the sort of happenstance discovery of materials that are celebrated about shelf browsing and a way to compare the productivity of each college and department at our university. It also illustrates our institution's changes in emphasis over time. **NEXT STEPS** Visualizations have vast potential for creating engaging user interfaces for digital library content. We would like to explore how

people are using the visualization as we move forward with this process to visualize multiple collections.

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